

***APOE* ε4-related differences in brain structure, function, and connectivity at midlife:**

A scoping review

Rikki Lissaman^{a,b,*}, Sidra Anjum^c, Andrea Quaiattini^d, and M. Natasha Rajah^{a,e}

^aDepartment of Psychiatry, McGill University, Montreal, QC, Canada

^bDepartment of Psychology, Royal Holloway, University of London, Egham, Surrey, UK

^cCentre for Addiction and Mental Health, Toronto, ON, Canada

^dSchulich Library of Physical Sciences, Life Sciences, and Engineering, McGill University, QC, Canada

^eDepartment of Psychology, Toronto Metropolitan University, Toronto, ON, Canada

*Corresponding author: Rikki Lissaman (rikki.lissaman@mail.mcgill.ca)

Abstract word count (excluding keywords): 197

Manuscript word count (excluding abstract, tables, figures, references): 6,437

Number of graphics (tables, figures, or appendices): 5

Number of references: 98

- We review *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in the middle-aged brain.
- Current research provides little evidence of robust differences.
- Small, non-representative samples were prominent.
- Few studies considered the role of sex-specific factors or ethnocultural diversity.

Abstract

Background

The apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) ϵ 4 allele is a major genetic risk factor for late-onset Alzheimer's disease (AD), yet there is little consensus about how and when the allele exerts its influence on the brain.

Methods

In this scoping review, we synthesized research examining *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences on MRI-derived measures of brain structure, function, and connectivity in cognitively unimpaired, middle-aged adults (aged 40-65 years). Four online databases (Ovid MEDLINE, Ovid Embase, Ovid PsycINFO, Scopus) were searched on July 11, 2024, and forward/backward reference searching was conducted on identified studies. We extracted data on sample characteristics, methods, and key *APOE* ϵ 4-related results.

Results

Our pre-registered search strategy identified 30 relevant studies. Overall, we found little evidence of robust, consistent differences between *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers at midlife, especially in relation to brain structure. However, among the studies identified, small samples were common, and limited consideration was afforded to factors such as sex and ethnocultural diversity.

Conclusion

Overall, the existing literature indicates that *APOE* ϵ 4 exerts little, if any, influence on brain structure at midlife, while differences in brain function and connectivity remain poorly characterized.

Keywords: Apolipoprotein E; midlife; brain structure; brain function; structural connectivity; functional connectivity.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 The human apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) gene, located on chromosome 19, encodes a
3 multi-functional protein, APOE, originally identified for its role in lipid metabolism (Mahley,
4 1988, 2016). There are three common allelic variants of the *APOE* gene: $\epsilon 2$, $\epsilon 3$, and $\epsilon 4$. The
5 APOE protein isoforms produced by these three alleles differ in their amino acid sequences at
6 only two positions (Rall et al., 1982; Weisgraber et al., 1981). Although small, these single
7 amino acid differences alter the structure and function of APOE (Huang & Mahley, 2014;
8 Mahley, 2016) and, in turn, have significant implications for an individual's risk of developing
9 late-onset Alzheimer's disease (AD; Corder et al., 1993). Relative to the most common *APOE*
10 genotype ($\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$), possession of the $\epsilon 4$ allele is associated with a ~2- to 4-fold and ~8- to-12-
11 fold increase in AD risk among heterozygote and homozygotes, respectively (Belloy et al.,
12 2019; Farrer et al., 1997). Estimates of lifetime risk for AD, as opposed to odds ratios, indicate
13 that the risk conferred by *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ is closer in magnitude to major genes in Mendelian diseases
14 than to genetic loci identified through genome-wide association studies (Genin et al., 2011).
15 *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ is also strongly associated with earlier and more advanced accumulation of amyloid-
16 β (Jansen et al., 2015, 2022; Sperling et al., 2020), a cardinal pathological feature of AD (Deture
17 & Dickson, 2019). Accordingly, although not all *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers ultimately develop AD, the
18 allele is widely recognized as a major genetic risk factor for late-onset AD.

19 Given the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -AD link, there is considerable research interest in understanding
20 how and when the allele exerts its influence on the brain. To this end, magnetic resonance
21 imaging (MRI) – a non-invasive imaging modality capable of evaluating brain structure,
22 function, and connectivity in vivo – has been widely adopted. To date, however, results have
23 been mixed. Among older adults, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ has been associated with lower gray matter volume
24 in regions implicated in AD, most notably the hippocampus, although findings are not
25 consistent (e.g., Honea et al., 2009; Lacey et al., 2024; Lyall et al., 2019; for reviews, see

26 Cherbuin et al., 2007; Fouquet et al., 2014). Studies using diffusion MRI to probe *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -
27 related differences in the microstructural properties of white matter – the brain’s structural
28 connections – have likewise produced heterogenous findings, both in terms of the
29 presence/absence of differences and the tracts implicated (e.g., Cavado et al., 2017; Heise et
30 al., 2011, 2024; Lacey et al., 2024; Lyall et al., 2014). In terms of brain function, task-evoked
31 functional MRI (fMRI) studies utilising episodic memory paradigms have reported higher and
32 lower activation levels in older $\epsilon 4$ carriers compared to non-carriers, as well as null effects
33 (McDonough et al., 2020). To account for these inconsistencies, some researchers have turned
34 to the prodromal hypothesis (Foster et al., 2013; Smith et al., 1998), which posits that $\epsilon 4$ -related
35 differences in brain health and cognition emerge late in life (~65+ years), fueled by greater
36 levels of AD pathology (e.g., amyloid- β) among $\epsilon 4$ carriers who will ultimately develop AD
37 (O’Donoghue et al., 2018). According to this perspective, inconsistencies between studies may
38 be driven by the incidental inclusion (or exclusion) of older $\epsilon 4$ carriers in the prodromal phase
39 of AD.

40 However, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in brain structure, function, and connectivity
41 have been observed much earlier in the adult lifespan, decades prior to the onset of significant
42 levels of AD pathology. For instance, several studies have reported that young adult $\epsilon 4$ carriers
43 compared to non-carriers exhibit higher levels of functional activation and connectivity,
44 especially in AD-vulnerable regions such as the hippocampus and posteromedial cortex
45 (Dennis et al., 2010; Filbey et al., 2006; Filippini et al., 2009; Hodgetts et al., 2019; Kunz et
46 al., 2015; Shine et al., 2015). Recent work has further reported an association between
47 heightened memory-related activation in posteromedial cortex and subsequent amyloid- β
48 burden in older $\epsilon 4$ carriers (Fischer et al., 2025). Such findings have led some to propose
49 lifespan accounts, whereby *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ induces a prolonged pattern of “hyperactivation”,
50 maintained throughout early-/mid-adulthood, predisposing specific brain networks to the

51 accumulation of AD pathology (Corriveau-Lecavalier et al., 2024; Jagust & Mormino, 2011).
52 Other researchers, however, have argued that neural differences in early adulthood may be
53 independent of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$'s role in AD (Palmer et al., 2023; Trachtenberg, Filippini, Cheeseman
54 et al., 2012; Trachtenberg, Filippini, Ebmeier et al., 2012). Proponents of the antagonistic
55 pleiotropy hypothesis (Han & Bondi, 2008; Tuminello & Han, 2011), for example, argue that
56 possession of the $\epsilon 4$ allele is evolutionary advantageous in early life but detrimental in later
57 life. In this context, heightened levels of activation among young adult $\epsilon 4$ carriers are
58 considered beneficial, unrelated to later AD risk (O'Donoghue et al., 2018). It is currently
59 unclear whether these benefits are maintained into midlife, as some have suggested (e.g.,
60 Zokaei et al., 2017), or whether midlife represents a transition period characterized by minimal
61 $\epsilon 4$ -related differences as the allele's influence shifts from advantageous to disadvantageous
62 (Salvato, 2015).

63 Despite this, little is currently known about *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in the brain at
64 midlife. Although historically understudied, midlife – broadly defined as ages 40 to 65 years –
65 is increasingly recognized as a pivotal point in the adult lifespan, shaping both normal and
66 pathological brain health trajectories (Dohm-Hansen et al., 2024; LaPlume et al., 2025). Many
67 factors, both biological (e.g., menopause) and lifestyle (e.g., physical exercise, diet), contribute
68 to the importance of this period and its impact on the brain and cognition (Lachman et al., 2015;
69 Park & Festini, 2016; Thurston et al., 2025). Nevertheless, it remains to be seen whether midlife
70 also marks a transition point for the influence of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$. In terms of cognition, findings to
71 date have been mixed, providing little evidence of a well-defined cognitive profile associated
72 with *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ at midlife (Lancaster et al., 2017). However, this does not preclude the presence
73 of neural differences. For instance, lifespan accounts specifically argue that while *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -
74 related “hyperactivation” is present throughout midlife, it is a precursor to later life cognitive
75 decline (Corriveau-Lecavalier et al., 2024; Jagust & Mormino, 2011). To assess such

76 possibilities and inform our understanding of when and how *APOE* ϵ 4 influences the brain, a
77 comprehensive review of the extant literature is warranted. To our knowledge, only one review
78 has specifically targeted midlife (Habib et al., 2017), yet the authors did not incorporate a lower
79 age cut-off, leading to the inclusion of many studies containing younger adults, complicating
80 interpretation.

81 In this scoping review, we attempt to address this knowledge gap. Our primary aim was
82 to systematically summarize what is currently known about *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences on
83 MRI-derived measures of brain structure, function, and connectivity in cognitively unimpaired,
84 middle-aged adults (aged 40-65 years). Our secondary aim was to summarize the methods used
85 to date, highlighting potential issues and outstanding questions for future research.

86 **2. Methods**

87 We used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
88 extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist (Tricco et al., 2018) to ensure this
89 scoping review was transparently and clearly described. Ethical approval was not required.

90 **2.1. Protocol and registration**

91 Our protocol was developed a priori and pre-registered on the Open Science Framework
92 (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5S4K9>). No substantive deviations were made. However,
93 during screening, we encountered studies that led us to add additional details, clarifying our
94 approach. All such clarifications are provided in the relevant sections below.

95 **2.2. Information sources and search strategy**

96 The search strategy was developed for Ovid MEDLINE by a subject librarian (A.Q.)
97 working alongside a member of the review team (R.L.). Once finalized, the search strategy was
98 translated to Ovid Embase, Ovid PsycINFO, and Scopus. A combination of text-word and
99 controlled vocabulary terms were used to target key concepts of interest: *APOE* and MRI-
100 derived measures of brain structure, function, and connectivity. To maximize inclusivity,

101 search terms related to midlife were not included. Instead, we screened studies for relevance.
102 To limit the number of publications requiring screening, however, we included a term to
103 remove animal only studies, where possible.

104 All searches were run on July 11, 2024. No language limits were applied. The full
105 search strategy is provided in the Supplementary Material. For completeness, we also
106 performed forward and backward reference searching of studies that passed full-text review.
107 Forward reference searching was performed using Scopus and restricted to studies published
108 on or before July 11, 2024.

109 **2.3. Eligibility criteria**

110 All studies identified in our searches were assessed against multi-stage eligibility
111 criteria. First, studies had to be published in a peer-reviewed journal. Owing to the language
112 proficiency of the authors, studies also had to be written in English. Second, studies had to
113 include a distinct group of cognitively unimpaired, middle-aged adults. For this review, we
114 define “cognitively unimpaired” as the absence of participants with neurological/psychiatric
115 disorders and “middle-aged adults” as those aged between 40 and 65 years (Dohm-Hansen et
116 al., 2024). To meet this age criterion, studies had to explicitly state the age range of the included
117 participants or the age range used for (initial) recruitment. In addition, if studies included more
118 than one age group, they had to include an *APOE* ϵ 4 comparison within the middle-aged group.
119 Third, studies had to use MRI to examine brain structure, function, or connectivity. For this
120 review, “structure” refers to volumetric and/or cortical thickness measures derived from
121 structural MRI, whereas “function” refers to task-evoked BOLD signal change (i.e.,
122 activation/deactivation), assessed using fMRI. We use the term “connectivity” to refer to the
123 temporal synchronicity of the BOLD fMRI signal across regions during task or rest (i.e., task-
124 based or resting-state functional connectivity) and diffusion MRI-derived measures assessing
125 the microstructural properties of white matter (i.e., structural connectivity). We thus excluded

126 studies using MRI methods that do not assess these neural properties, as well as non-MRI
127 methods. This ensured that we covered studies examining the neural properties of interest at a
128 broadly similar spatial and temporal scale. Fourth, studies had to directly compare a group of
129 *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers to one or more groups of non-carriers. We did not include studies that adopted
130 genome-wide association-like analyses, whereby associations with many single nucleotide
131 polymorphisms in/near the *APOE* locus were examined. Moreover, if studies incorporated
132 other factors (e.g., family history of dementia), we included them only if one of two conditions
133 were met: (1) a formal statistical comparison between a carrier and non-carrier group at the
134 same level of the other variable was presented (e.g., *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers with a positive family
135 history of dementia vs. *APOE* ϵ 4 non-carriers with a positive family history of dementia); (2)
136 a “main effect” of *APOE* ϵ 4 was reported from the statistical model. It was not enough to adjust
137 for *APOE* ϵ 4 carrier status.

138 **2.4. Screening and data extraction**

139 Our search results were uploaded into Covidence (Veritas Health Innovation,
140 Melbourne, Australia) for title and abstract screening. This screening step was performed
141 independently by two reviewers (R.L., S.A.) who adopted a liberal approach, excluding studies
142 only if there was evidence that they did not meet our stated eligibility criteria. For example, if
143 a study abstract did not include an age range, we initially included it (if other criteria were
144 satisfied). Disagreements were discussed and, where necessary, submitted to a third reviewer
145 (M.N.R.) for mediation. All studies that passed this initial step were then subject to full-text
146 review, again completed independently by two reviewers (R.L., S.A.) and mediated by a third
147 (M.N.R.). This step was performed more conservatively. For example, if a study passed title
148 and abstract screening due to lack of evidence (e.g., no age range in the abstract), it was
149 excluded during full-text review if the age range was either (a) not specified in the methods or
150 (b) incompatible with our definition of midlife.

151 Data from studies that passed full-text review were extracted by one reviewer (R.L.)
152 using a project-specific Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The extracted data included general
153 publication information (e.g., title, publication year), methods (e.g., cross-
154 sectional/longitudinal design, imaging modalities used), sample characteristics (e.g., sample
155 size), and key *APOE* ϵ 4-related results.

156 **2.5. Synthesis of results**

157 Studies were grouped according to whether they assessed brain structure, function, or
158 connectivity. We initially planned to include separate structural and functional connectivity
159 sections. However, due to the small number of studies using diffusion MRI, we instead grouped
160 these studies together. Note that studies adopting a multi-modal approach were included in
161 more than one category. Moreover, given the variable statistical methods and corresponding *p*-
162 value thresholds used across studies, we discuss results according to the methods used in each
163 study, as done elsewhere (Trachtenberg, Filippini, & Mackay, 2012).

164 **3. Results**

165 **3.1. Search results**

166 A PRISMA flow diagram outlining our search results is provided in Figure 1. After
167 removing duplicates, our initial searches yielded 7,092 studies. Of these, 6,932 were excluded
168 during title and abstract screening, leaving 160 studies for full-text review. In total, 135 studies
169 were subsequently excluded. Reasons for exclusion were: age range not reported ($n = 62$); age
170 range did not fall between 40 and 65 years ($n = 61$); lack of relevant *APOE* ϵ 4 comparison (n
171 $= 11$); did not use neuroimaging modality of interest ($n = 1$). Given the large number of studies
172 excluded for failing to report an age range, we conducted a follow-up analysis to estimate the
173 age range for these studies. As shown in the Supplementary Material, only one of the 62 studies
174 reported values potentially consistent with a range between 40 and 65 years, suggesting our
175 age criteria were appropriate for this midlife-specific review. The reference lists of the

176 remaining 25 studies were then scanned, leading to the identification of three additional studies
177 (O'Brien et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; McKeever et al., 2020). All three studies included
178 relevant *APOE* ϵ 4-related analyses, even though *APOE* was not mentioned in the title or
179 abstract. Forward reference searching, performed in Scopus, led to the identification of two
180 further studies (Newton et al., 2024; Okonkwo et al., 2014). These studies likewise did not
181 mention *APOE* ϵ 4 in the title or abstract. In total, therefore, we identified 30 studies eligible
182 for this scoping review.

183 **3.2. Study characteristics**

184 Among the 30 studies identified, 25 focused on brain structure (83.3%), 10 focused on
185 brain function (33.3%), and 7 focused on brain structural/functional connectivity (23.3%).
186 These numbers do not sum to 30 as more than a third of the included studies were multi-modal
187 ($n = 11$, 36.7%). Collapsed across modality, most studies ($n = 25$, 83.3%) adopted a cross-
188 sectional design or reported only cross-sectional analyses of *APOE* ϵ 4. In terms of sample size,
189 substantial variability was evident. Median total sample size across studies was 92.5 (range =
190 32-611). When separated according to the neural properties examined, however, we found that
191 studies focused on structure tended to include larger samples ($Mdn = 122$) than those focused
192 on function ($Mdn = 52$) or connectivity ($Mdn = 46$). Surprisingly, we found little evidence to
193 indicate that sample sizes had increased over the last two decades (Supplementary Figure 1).

194 Variability was also evident in the age range of participants (Figure 2). For instance,
195 while all but one study (Cherbuin et al., 2008) included individuals aged 50-55 years, those
196 aged 40-55 and 60-65 years were less consistently included. In terms of geography, we found
197 that most studies were conducted in North America ($n = 17$, 56.7%) and Europe ($n = 12$, 40%),
198 although one study was conducted in Oceania ($n = 1$, 3.3%). None of the studies included were
199 conducted in Africa, Asia, or South America. Furthermore, only 8 studies provided information
200 on the racial/ethnic composition of the included participants (Fortel et al., 2020, 2022; Nemes

201 et al., 2023; Nerattini et al., 2023; Okonkwo et al., 2012, 2014; Panizzon et al., 2010; Ritchie
202 et al., 2017). The reported values demonstrate that most of the participants ($\geq 75\%$) identified
203 as white or “Caucasian”.

204 Almost all studies included here were mixed-sex¹ studies ($n = 27$, 90%). Among the
205 three single-sex studies, two focused on males (Fennema-Notestine et al., 2011; Panizzon et
206 al., 2010) and one focused on females (Nerattini et al., 2023). Notably, excluding one study
207 that did not report figures for sex (Reiman et al., 1998), all mixed-sex studies included more
208 females than males. It was surprising, therefore, that only four studies in this midlife review
209 mentioned menopause. Of these, two discussed menopause in their discussion (Evans et al.,
210 2013; Nemes et al., 2023), one reported the number of (self-reported) menopausal females in
211 the sample but did not collect further details (Rajah et al., 2017), and one (female-only) study
212 reported the number of pre-, peri-, and post-menopausal females included, while examining
213 associations between gonadotropins and neuroimaging biomarkers (Nerattini et al., 2023).
214 None of the studies examined the potential link between *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences and
215 menopausal status, despite the skew toward females.

216 3.3. Brain structure

217 Table 1 provides an overview of the 25 studies that examined differences in brain
218 structure between midlife *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-carriers. Most of these studies focused on
219 volumetric measures, although some examined cortical thickness. Whole-brain analyses tended
220 to use voxel-based morphometry, but others analyzed global/whole-brain measures (e.g., total
221 grey matter volume). Region of interest (ROI) analyses were heavily focused on the

¹ The terms “sex” and “gender” were used somewhat interchangeable in the reviewed studies. For consistency, we use the term sex throughout this scoping review. Further, as the included studies overwhelmingly used self-report to categorize individuals as male/female or man/woman, we also use terms such as “mixed-sex studies” and “single-sex studies”. This reflects the state of the literature, which has hitherto largely ignored intersex individuals, as well as transgender and gender non-binary individuals.

222 hippocampus. Of the 19 studies reporting an ROI analysis, 17 (89.5%) included the
223 hippocampus as an ROI, while 10 (52.9%) included the hippocampus as the only ROI.

224 Among the 25 studies reviewed, 20 (80%) did not observe a statistically significant
225 difference between *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers. While null findings were prominent in
226 studies employing voxel-based morphometry, studies examining whole-brain and ROI-specific
227 measures of volume and cortical thickness also reported null findings (Table 1). Moreover,
228 even among the 5 studies reporting at least one significant *APOE* ϵ 4-related difference
229 (Dounavi et al., 2020; Dowell et al., 2016; Fennema-Notestine et al., 2011; Okonkwo et al.,
230 2012; Panizzon et al., 2010), no consistent pattern was evident. For instance, in a single-sex
231 (male-only) study, Fennema-Notestine et al. (2011) reported that ϵ 4 carriers possessed thinner
232 frontal cortices but thicker fusiform cortices than ϵ 4 non-carriers. However, no such differences
233 were observed in the thickness of parahippocampal cortex, despite another study reporting ϵ 4-
234 related differences in this region at midlife (Dowell et al., 2016). Fennema-Notestine et al. also
235 observed no difference in hippocampal volume, consistent with most midlife studies reviewed
236 here, but inconsistent with a study conducted on participants from the same male-only cohort
237 (Panizzon et al., 2010). That said, the negative influence of *APOE* ϵ 4 on hippocampal volume
238 in the latter study was only evident when the interaction between the allele and testosterone
239 was included in the statistical model (Panizzon et al., 2010).

240 The focus on the whole hippocampus and not its subfields may also explain the lack of
241 ϵ 4-related differences in studies targeting this structure. While terminology varies, it is
242 generally accepted that the hippocampus includes distinct subfields: the cornu ammonis fields,
243 dentate gyrus, and subiculum (Insausti & Amaral, 2012). There is evidence to suggest that these
244 subfields are differentially impacted in the early stages of AD (Young et al., 2020) and thus
245 differences between *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers may likewise be present earlier in the
246 lifespan. Accordingly, by averaging across subfields, it is possible that important differences

247 were missed. This view is partially supported by findings from Dounavi et al. (2020) who
248 reported that the volume of the hippocampal molecular layer, but not other hippocampal
249 subfields, was lower in $\epsilon 4$ carriers. However, the same group failed to replicate this result in a
250 subsequent study adopting a different method for the automated segmentation and processing
251 of hippocampal subfields (Dounavi et al., 2022). Additionally, two other studies featured in
252 this review – one including manual segmentation of hippocampal subfields at 3T (McKeever
253 et al., 2020), one including semi-automated segmentation of hippocampal subfields at 7T
254 (Newton et al., 2024) – failed to identify $\epsilon 4$ -related differences.

255 **3.4. Brain function**

256 Table 2 provides an overview of the 10 midlife studies that used fMRI to examine
257 *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences on brain function. Analytical approaches varied across studies:
258 four adopted whole-brain analyses (40%), two adopted ROI-specific analyses (20%), and four
259 conducted mixed analyses (40%). As with studies of brain structure, ROI-specific analyses
260 often focused on the hippocampus and medial temporal lobe, although other regions (e.g.,
261 posterior cingulate cortex) were also examined. Interestingly, many of these midlife fMRI
262 studies ($n = 7$, 70%) reported at least one significant difference between $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-
263 carriers, but variability was present.

264 Given the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -AD link, it is unsurprising that most tasks were memory-related (n
265 = 8, 72.7%). Old/new recognition memory tasks were the most common ($n = 5$). Results from
266 these studies were inconclusive and sometimes contradictory. For instance, while Johnson et
267 al. (2006) did not observe *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in novelty-related activation, Trivedi
268 et al. (2006) reported lower novelty-related activation in the right hippocampus among $\epsilon 4$
269 carriers relative to $\epsilon 4$ non-carriers. Further, when examining familiarity-related activation,
270 Trivedi et al. (2006) did not identify differences related to *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ (see also Okonkwo et al.,
271 2014), despite another study reporting lower activation among $\epsilon 4$ carriers (relative to $\epsilon 4$ non-

272 carriers) in left dorsal posterior cingulate cortex/precuneus (Xu et al., 2009). Finally, while
273 Evans et al. (2020) did not detect a significant *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ group difference, they did find that
274 non-carriers – but not $\epsilon 4$ carriers – exhibited greater activation in left hippocampus at encoding
275 for remembered vs. forgotten items. Caution is warranted, however, as this was the only study
276 to examine activation during the encoding phase of an old/new recognition task.

277 Nonetheless, differences in encoding-related activation between those with and without
278 $\epsilon 4$ have been reported in another midlife memory study, albeit using a different paradigm.
279 Rajah et al. (2017) used a spatial context memory task and scanned participants at encoding
280 and retrieval. At encoding, participants viewed photographs of faces presented to the left or
281 right of fixation and were required to remember the item and its location. At retrieval,
282 participants were asked to indicate which face they previously saw on the left or right,
283 depending on the cue. The number of items was manipulated, producing low- and high-load
284 conditions. The authors reported greater activation in the right hippocampus during low-load
285 encoding among $\epsilon 4$ carriers with a family history of AD relative to $\epsilon 4$ non-carriers with a family
286 history of AD, as well as those without either risk factor. The authors also observed that, among
287 participants with a family history of AD, possession of the $\epsilon 4$ allele was related to differential
288 activation of fusiform cortex during encoding and retrieval.

289 In a separate study, Newton et al. (2024) used a spatial memory task to explore the
290 association between AD risk factors, including *APOE* $\epsilon 4$, and grid cell-like activation in
291 posteromedial entorhinal cortex. Using ultra-high resolution (7T) MRI, the authors scanned
292 participants from the PREVENT Dementia cohort (Ritchie et al., 2024) while they watched
293 videos of themselves passively navigate through a three-dimensional room containing seven
294 everyday items. Participants were instructed to learn the locations of these items, which
295 changed across videos. The walls of the room, each decorated with items, did not change,
296 providing orientation clues. At the end of each video, participants were presented with three

297 images of each item – one in the correct location, two in incorrect locations – and asked to
298 identify the correct one. For this review, the crucial finding was that *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ alone was not
299 associated with grid cell-like activation in posteromedial entorhinal cortex. While this task
300 differed substantially to that use by Rajah et al. (2017), it is notable that only one of these
301 studies identified an $\epsilon 4$ effect at midlife, despite both tasks requiring participants to identify
302 the spatial location of previously seen items.

303 The final memory-related task focused on prospective memory: remembering to
304 perform a future planned action (Evans et al., 2014). In this study, participants were presented
305 with playing cards, presented sequentially. They were required to press a button if the suit was
306 hearts or spades (sort trials) but withhold their response if the suit was clubs or diamonds
307 (withhold trials). While doing so, participants also had to remember to press a different button
308 if the card was a seven regardless of the suit (prospective memory trial). The authors observed
309 an association between *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ and activation evoked by this task but only on prospective
310 memory trials. Specifically, during prospective memory trials, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers were found to
311 exhibit lower levels of activation than non-carriers in extrastriate cortex and the right superior
312 parietal lobe.

313 *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in extrastriate cortex function have also been reported
314 using a non-mnemonic paradigm, potentially suggesting that the allele has a detrimental impact
315 on aspects of the visual system at midlife. Evans et al. (2013) used a covert attention task in
316 which participants were asked to indicate whether an item appeared on the left or right of screen
317 following a cue, which was predictive of item location (valid cue) or not (invalid cue). Evans
318 et al. found that $\epsilon 4$ carriers demonstrated lower activation than non-carriers in extrastriate
319 cortex independent of cue type (valid, invalid). However, in a subsequent study, the same group
320 failed to observe differences in activation between groups when using the exact same covert

321 attention task (Evans et al., 2014). Accordingly, given the lack of internal replication, it is
322 unclear whether differences in extrastriate cortex function are robust.

323 While nearly all tasks used to explore *APOE* $\epsilon 4$'s influence at midlife were memory-
324 or attention-related, Johnson et al. (2007) used a metacognitive self-appraisal task. In this
325 paradigm, a series of adjectives were presented, and participants were asked to indicate whether
326 the adjectives described their own traits/abilities (self-referential condition) or were of positive
327 valence (non-referential condition). The authors did not identify *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences,
328 but their analysis was restricted to regions not showing an interaction between the allele and
329 family history of AD. Despite not being the primary focus of this review, Johnson et al. did
330 find that $\epsilon 4$ carriers without a family history of AD showed greater activation for referential
331 self-appraisal in left superior frontal gyrus, left anterior cingulate, and retrosplenial areas in left
332 superior frontal gyrus, left anterior cingulate gyrus, and retrosplenial cortex relative to all other
333 groups. Yet, while differences between $\epsilon 4$ carriers/non-carriers without a family history of AD
334 could point to an allele-specific impact at midlife, the lack of difference between $\epsilon 4$
335 carriers/non-carriers with a family history of AD complicates this interpretation.

336 **3.5. Brain connectivity**

337 Table 3 provides an overview of the seven midlife studies that examined differences in
338 brain connectivity between middle-aged *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-carriers. Five reported
339 significant $\epsilon 4$ -related differences, representing a majority (71.4%). However, the methods and,
340 in turn, the form of connectivity probed varied across studies. One study used diffusion MRI
341 (Evans et al., 2020), three studies used resting-state fMRI (Dowell et al., 2016; Goveas et al.,
342 2013; Li et al., 2014), while an additional three studies used some combination of the two
343 (Fortel et al., 2020, 2022; Korthauer et al., 2018).

344 The study to exclusively use diffusion MRI did so to examine *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related
345 differences in bilateral hippocampal microstructure, assessed via the orientation dispersion

346 index (ODI; Evans et al., 2020). However, the authors found that $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-carriers
347 did not differ in bilateral hippocampal ODI. Nevertheless, Evans et al. did observe a difference
348 between groups in the association between hippocampal ODI and old/new recognition
349 memory, with a positive trend evident only for $\epsilon 4$ non-carriers. It is possible, therefore, that
350 *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ may not impact the microstructural properties of the hippocampus but may impact
351 how these properties relate to and support memory.

352 Among the three studies to exclusively use resting-state fMRI, there was variation in
353 the analytical methods used. Goveas et al. (2013) and Li et al. (2014) both conducted seed-
354 based analyses, examining differences in functional connectivity associated with specific
355 regions. Goveas et al. focused on core components of different resting-state functional
356 networks: posterior cingulate cortex (default mode network), dorsolateral prefrontal cortex
357 (executive control network), and orbital anterior insula (salience network). Li et al., conversely,
358 focused on the hippocampus. Despite this, both studies reported patterns of lower functional
359 connectivity among $\epsilon 4$ carriers relative to non-carriers; Goveas et al. identified this pattern
360 within the default mode and executive control networks, while Li et al. identified this pattern
361 between the hippocampus and several regions. The exception was that of the salience network,
362 where Goveas et al. identified increased connectivity among $\epsilon 4$ carriers relative to non-carriers.
363 By contrast, Dowell et al. (2016) used independent components analysis to identify resting-
364 state networks and test for *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences. Although the authors identified eight
365 such networks, including the default mode and executive control networks, no carrier/non-
366 carrier differences were evident in their midlife sample. This contradicts the results reported
367 by Goveas et al., raising questions about the role of methodological choices.

368 Three studies have adopted an alternative approach, combining both diffusion MRI and
369 resting-state fMRI (Fortel et al., 2020, 2022; Korthauer et al., 2018). For example, Korthauer
370 et al. (2018) extracted graph theoretical properties from three networks – a functional network

371 derived from resting-state fMRI, a structural network derived from diffusion MRI, and an
372 integrated functional-structural network (the “resting-state structural connectome”) – and then
373 examined differences between middle-aged *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers and non-carriers. While the
374 authors did not find differences in the properties of the functional and structural networks, they
375 observed differences in the resting-state structural connectome. Specifically, they found that
376 ϵ 4 carriers exhibited lower levels of global and local efficiency in this combined network.
377 Korthauer et al. also reported differences in the properties of hub networks and lower resilience
378 to node failure, especially once more than 10% of hubs were removed. These results highlight
379 the potential utility of combining resting-state fMRI and diffusion MRI to probe connectivity
380 and indicate that such an approach may reveal subtle *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences at midlife.
381 Concordantly, two further studies have demonstrated that *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers, in particular
382 female *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers, exhibit a global shift towards hyper-excitation in the resting-state
383 structural connectome (Fortel et al., 2020) and a lower tolerance to network dysfunction (Fortel
384 et al., 2022) at midlife.

385 **4. Discussion**

386 **4.1. Summary of findings**

387 In this scoping review, we synthesized research examining *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences
388 in brain structure, function, and connectivity at midlife. The reviewed MRI studies provide
389 little evidence to indicate that middle-aged *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers exhibit consistent differences in
390 brain structure relative to non-carriers. Variation in study design, analytical approach, and
391 outcome measure do not appear to offer a coherent explanation for these null findings. Among
392 studies assessing brain function and connectivity, *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences were more
393 commonly reported. However, there was marked variation in the regions/networks implicated
394 and the direction of the reported differences. The neural profile of *APOE* ϵ 4 at midlife thus
395 remains poorly characterized.

396 The absence of robust, consistent differences in the reviewed studies may reflect a
397 genuine lack of *APOE* ϵ 4-related differences in the brain at midlife. Such an explanation is
398 consistent with the prodromal hypothesis, which proposes that ϵ 4-related differences in the
399 brain and cognition emerge relatively late in the adult lifespan, driven by the heightened burden
400 of AD pathology among ϵ 4 carriers who will go on to develop the disease (Foster et al., 2013;
401 Smith et al., 1998). In this light, it is perhaps unsurprising that the reviewed studies reported
402 many null findings. However, the lack of a distinct neural profile among middle-aged *APOE*
403 ϵ 4 carriers is also arguably consistent with the antagonistic pleiotropy hypothesis (Han &
404 Bondi, 2008; Tuminello & Han, 2011). Although some *APOE* studies have claimed to identify
405 examples of antagonistic pleiotropy in midlife (e.g., Zokaei et al., 2017), the hypothesis – as
406 originally stated – predicts subtle differences, if any, at midlife, as the allele’s influence shifts
407 from advantageous to disadvantageous (Breting et al., 2012; Salvato, 2015). It follows,
408 therefore, that the reviewed studies do not necessarily provide evidence that *APOE* ϵ 4-related
409 differences are driven entirely by pathology. Longitudinal studies are needed to determine
410 whether midlife differences in MRI-based measures, if present, are related to prodromal AD, a
411 necessary step for the development of imaging biomarkers (O’Donoghue et al., 2018).

412 It is less clear how lifespan accounts can explain the results from the reviewed studies.
413 These accounts propose that the *APOE* ϵ 4 allele induces a prolonged pattern of hyperactivation
414 that is present across early- and mid-life, predisposing vulnerable brain networks to AD
415 pathology and later dysfunction (Corriveau-Lecavalier et al., 2024; Jagust & Mormino, 2011).
416 Yet, consistent with a review of studies on older adults (McDonough et al., 2020), the reported
417 differences in patterns of task-evoked fMRI activation were extremely mixed. In fact, of the 10
418 fMRI studies identified, only two observed greater activation in middle-aged *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers
419 compared to non-carriers (Johnson et al., 2007; Rajah et al., 2017). Four studies even reported
420 the opposite pattern, linking *APOE* ϵ 4 with lower levels of task-evoked activation (Evans et

421 al., 2013, 2014; Trivedi et al., 2006; Xu et al., 2009). While the use of different paradigms and
422 stimuli place constraints on comparability across studies, it is nevertheless challenging to
423 reconcile these findings with claims that fMRI hyperactivation observed in young, at-risk
424 adults (e.g., Filippini et al., 2009) is maintained into midlife.

425 Another possibility is that the $\epsilon 4$ allele impacts brain health at midlife through
426 alternative mechanisms. For example, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ has been associated with cerebrovascular
427 dysfunction in aging and AD, including alterations in cerebral blood flow and blood-brain
428 barrier integrity (Chen et al., 2024; Palmer et al., 2023). Differences between $\epsilon 4$ carriers and
429 non-carriers in these vascular mechanisms have likewise been observed in studies of young
430 and middle-aged adults (Alruwais et al., 2022; Dounavi et al., 2021, 2023; Suri et al., 2015).
431 Such findings suggest that *APOE* $\epsilon 4$'s influence on the cerebrovascular system is more
432 prominent than its influence on brain structure, function, or connectivity. Consistent with this
433 notion, one large cross-sectional study of late middle-aged and older adults reported that *APOE*
434 $\epsilon 4$ was associated with greater white matter hyperintensity volumes, an indicator of poorer
435 cerebrovascular health, but not gray matter volume or white matter microstructure (Lyall et al.,
436 2019). Together, these findings provide evidence that *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ is linked to midlife brain health
437 but, crucially, not in the neural properties targeted in this scoping review.

438 A variety of methodological issues could have influenced the results reported, however,
439 contributing to a lack of $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in brain structure and/or variability in $\epsilon 4$ -related
440 differences in brain function/connectivity. One prominent issue is the widespread use of small
441 samples, which limits statistical power and increases the likelihood of missing a true "effect"
442 (i.e., a Type II error) (Button et al., 2013). In the reviewed studies, the median total sample size
443 was 92.5, which is comparable to *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related studies in young adults (*Mdn* = 62;
444 Kucikova et al., 2024) but provides insufficient power to reliably detect small effects. This is
445 relevant here as effect sizes associated with common genetic variants on neuroimaging

446 outcomes are typically small (Mitchell, 2017). While *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ may represent an exception to
447 this rule, a recent study of ~43,000 late middle-aged and older adults casts some doubt on this
448 (Heise et al., 2024). It is possible, therefore, that *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ does influence brain structure,
449 function, and/or connectivity at midlife, but most studies were simply underpowered to detect
450 it.

451 Another methodological issue was the lack of consideration for the roles of sex and
452 ethnocultural diversity. Regarding sex, we found that most studies included more females than
453 males, some to a greater extent than others, but few actively explored the influence of sex or
454 sex-related factors. Indeed, only four studies identified in this review even mentioned
455 menopause, despite the focus on midlife. This was surprising as the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ allele has long
456 been shown to have a greater impact on AD risk among females (Farrer et al., 1997), especially
457 among those aged 60-75 years (Belloy et al., 2023; Neu et al., 2017), potentially underpinned
458 by estrogen-*APOE* interactions (Gamache et al., 2020; Valencia-Olvera et al., 2023).
459 Regarding ethnocultural diversity, we found that few studies reported the racial/ethnic
460 breakdown of their samples. Among those that did, there was a clear skew towards white or
461 “Caucasian” individuals. Although unsurprising given the broader cognitive neuroscience
462 literature, the lack of studies including non-white individuals limits the generalizability of
463 results (Dotson & Duarte, 2020). This is particularly problematic for research on *APOE*, as
464 evidence suggests that the association between the $\epsilon 4$ allele and AD risk varies as a function of
465 race/ethnicity (Belloy et al., 2019, 2023; Farrer et al., 1997). Given this, we cannot rule out the
466 possibility that inconsistencies across studies were partly related to the differential composition
467 of the participants, both in terms of sex and ethnocultural diversity, as well as other health
468 factors (e.g., hormone replacement therapy, body mass index, hypertension). Future research
469 would greatly benefit from the inclusion of more diverse midlife samples, as well as a greater
470 consideration of menopause and related factors.

471 **4.2. Limitations**

472 Our scoping review has some limitations that should be considered. First, we focused
473 exclusively on studies published in peer-reviewed journals. It is thus possible that we missed
474 relevant research, which may be available as pre-prints, conference proceedings, or
475 dissertations. If publication bias was present, our focus on peer-reviewed studies may have
476 resulted in the over-representation of work reporting significant *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences.
477 However, the studies reviewed – many reporting null findings – cast some doubt on this.
478 Second, our scoping review included studies published as of July 11, 2024. Although this is an
479 unavoidable feature of reviews, we may have missed relevant work published since this date.
480 Third, we included studies only if the age range was reported and, crucially, if it fell between
481 40-65 years, a common definition of midlife (Dohm-Hansen et al., 2024). While we identified
482 30 studies meeting this criterion, this led to the exclusion of several studies that claimed to
483 focus on midlife. In this regard, our approach arguably placed a greater emphasis on specificity
484 than sensitivity (although see Supplementary Material).

485 **5. Conclusions**

486 The *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ allele is a major genetic risk factor for late-onset Alzheimer's disease,
487 yet its influence on the middle-aged brain is not well characterized. In this scoping review, we
488 aimed to address this by synthesizing research examining $\epsilon 4$ -related differences on MRI-
489 derived measures of brain structure, function, and connectivity among middle-aged adults.
490 While the current literature is dominated by small, non-representative samples, the available
491 evidence suggests that *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers and non-carriers do not exhibit robust, consistent
492 differences at midlife. This is especially true for measures of brain structure, although the
493 allele's influence on brain function and connectivity remains poorly delineated.

Acknowledgements: We are grateful to our respective institutions for their support.

Funding: This work was supported by Canada Research Chairs Program CRC-2022-00240, CIHR Sex & Gender Research Chair GS9-171369, and NSERC Discovery Grant RGPIN-2018-05761 awarded to M. N. Rajah, and a Canadian Consortium on Neurodegeneration in Aging (CCNA) – Women, Sex, Gender, & Dementia (WSGD) Postdoctoral Fellowship awarded to R. Lissaman.

Declarations of interests: None.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process: During the preparation of this work, the first author (R. Lissaman) used ChatGPT to rephrase limited sections of text, with the aim of improving manuscript readability. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

References

- Alruwais, N. M., Rusted, J. M., Tabet, N., & Dowell, N. G. (2022). Evidence of emerging BBB changes in mid-age apolipoprotein E epsilon-4 carriers. *Brain and Behavior*, *12*(12), e2806. <https://doi.org/10.1002/brb3.2806>
- Belloy, M. E., Andrews, S. J., Le Guen, Y., Cuccaro, M., Farrer, L. A., Napolioni, V., & Greicius, M. D. (2023). *APOE* genotype and Alzheimer disease risk across age, sex, and population ancestry. *JAMA Neurology*. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2023.3599>
- Belloy, M. E., Napolioni, V., & Greicius, M. D. (2019). A quarter century of APOE and Alzheimer's disease: Progress to date and the path forward. *Neuron*, *101*(5), 820–838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.01.056>
- Button, K. S., Ioannidis, J. P. A., Mokrysz, C., Nosek, B. A., Flint, J., Robinson, E. S. J., & Munafò, M. R. (2013). Power failure: Why small sample size undermines the reliability of neuroscience. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *14*(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3475>
- Cavedo, E., Lista, S., Rojkova, K., Chiesa, P. A., Houot, M., Brueggen, K., Blautzik, J., Bokde, A. L. W., Dubois, B., Barkhof, F., Pouwels, P. J. W., Teipel, S., & Hampel, H. (2017). Disrupted white matter structural networks in healthy older adult *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers – An international multicenter DTI study. *Neuroscience*, *357*, 119–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2017.05.048>
- Chen, F., Zhao, J., Meng, F., He, F., Ni, J., & Fu, Y. (2024). The vascular contribution of apolipoprotein E to Alzheimer's disease. *Brain*, *147*(9), 2946–2965. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awae156>
- Cherbuin, N., Anstey, K. J., Sachdev, P. S., Maller, J. J., Meslin, C., Mack, H. A., Wen, W., & Easteal, S. (2008). Total and regional gray matter volume Is not related to *APOE*E4*

- status in a community sample of middle-aged individuals. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series A*, 63(5), 501–504. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/63.5.501>
- Cherbuin, N., Leach, L. S., Christensen, H., & Anstey, K. J. (2007). Neuroimaging and *APOE* genotype: A systematic qualitative Review. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 24(5), 348–362. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000109150>
- Corder, E., Saunders, A., Strittmatter, W., Schmechel, D., Gaskell, P., Small, G., Roses, A., Haines, J., & Pericak-Vance, M. (1993). Gene dose of apolipoprotein E type 4 allele and the risk of Alzheimer’s disease in late onset families. *Science*, 261(5123), 921–923. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.8346443>
- Corriveau-Lecavalier, N., Adams, J. N., Fischer, L., Molloy, E. N., & Maass, A. (2024). Cerebral hyperactivation across the Alzheimer’s disease pathological cascade. *Brain Communications*, 6(6), fcae376. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcae376>
- Dennis, N. A., Browndyke, J. N., Stokes, J., Need, A., Burke, J. R., Welsh-Bohmer, K. A., & Cabeza, R. (2010). Temporal lobe functional activity and connectivity in young adult *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers. *Alzheimer’s & Dementia*, 6(4), 303–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2009.07.003>
- DeTure, M. A., & Dickson, D. W. (2019). The neuropathological diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease. *Molecular Neurodegeneration*, 14, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13024-019-0333-5>
- Dohm-Hansen, S., English, J. A., Lavelle, A., Fitzsimons, C. P., Lucassen, P. J., & Nolan, Y. M. (2024). The “middle-aging” brain. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 47(4), 259–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2024.02.001>
- Dotson, V. M., & Duarte, A. (2020). The importance of diversity in cognitive neuroscience. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1464(1), 181–191. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14268>

- Dounavi, M.-E., Low, A., McKiernan, E. F., Mak, E., Muniz-Terrera, G., Ritchie, K., Ritchie, C. W., Su, L., & O'Brien, J. T. (2021). Evidence of cerebral hemodynamic dysregulation in middle-aged APOE ϵ 4 carriers: The PREVENT-Dementia study. *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*, *41*(11), 2844–2855. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0271678X211020863>
- Dounavi, M.-E., Mak, E., Swann, P., Low, A., Muniz-Terrera, G., McKeever, A., Pope, M., Williams, G. B., Wells, K., Lawlor, B., Naci, L., Malhotra, P., Mackay, C., Koychev, I., Ritchie, K., Su, L., Ritchie, C. W., & O'Brien, J. T. (2023). Differential association of cerebral blood flow and anisocytosis in APOE ϵ 4 carriers at midlife. *Journal of Cerebral Blood Flow & Metabolism*, *43*(10), 1672–1684. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0271678X231173587>
- Dounavi, M.-E., Mak, E., Wells, K., Ritchie, K., Ritchie, C. W., Su, L., & O'Brien, J. T. (2020). Volumetric alterations in the hippocampal subfields of subjects at increased risk of dementia. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *91*, 36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2020.03.006>
- Dounavi, M.-E., Newton, C., Jenkins, N., Mak, E., Low, A., Muniz-Terrera, G., Williams, G. B., Lawlor, B., Naci, L., Malhotra, P., Mackay, C. E., Koychev, I., Ritchie, K., Ritchie, C. W., Su, L., & O'Brien, J. T. (2022). Macrostructural brain alterations at midlife are connected to cardiovascular and not inherited risk of future dementia: The PREVENT-Dementia study. *Journal of Neurology*, *269*(8), 4299–4309. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-022-11061-7>
- Dowell, N. G., Evans, S. L., Tofts, P. S., King, S. L., Tabet, N., & Rusted, J. M. (2016). Structural and resting-state MRI detects regional brain differences in young and mid-age healthy APOE-e4 carriers compared with non-APOE-e4 carriers. *NMR in Biomedicine*, *29*(5), 614–624. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nbm.3502>

- Evans, S., Dowell, N. G., Tabet, N., Tofts, P. S., King, S. L., Gray, M., & Rusted, J. M. (2013). Nicotine effects on attentional reorienting in mid-age adults, and interactions with apolipoprotein E status. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, *27*(11), 1007–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881113499828>
- Evans, S., Dowell, N. G., Tabet, N., Tofts, P. S., King, S. L., & Rusted, J. M. (2014). Cognitive and neural signatures of the APOE E4 allele in mid-aged adults. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *35*(7), 1615–1623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2014.01.145>
- Evans, S. L., Dowell, N. G., Prowse, F., Tabet, N., King, S. L., & Rusted, J. M. (2020). Mid age *APOE* ϵ 4 carriers show memory-related functional differences and disrupted structure-function relationships in hippocampal regions. *Scientific Reports*, *10*, 3110. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-59272-0>
- Farrer, L. A., Cupples, L. A., Haines, J. L., Hyman, B., Kukull, W. A., Mayeux, R., Myers, R. H., Pericak-Vance, M. A., Risch, N., van Duijn, C. M., & for the APOE and Alzheimer Disease Meta Analysis Consortium. (1997). Effects of age, sex, and ethnicity on the association between apolipoprotein E genotype and Alzheimer disease: A meta-analysis. *JAMA*, *278*(16), 1349–1356. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1997.03550160069041>
- Fennema-Notestine, C., Panizzon, M. S., Thompson, W. R., Chen, C.-H., Eyler, L. T., Fischl, B., Franz, C. E., Grant, M. D., Jak, A. J., Jernigan, T. L., Lyons, M. J., Neale, M. C., Seidman, L. J., Tsuang, M. T., Xian, H., Dale, A. M., & Kremen, W. S. (2011). Presence of ApoE ϵ 4 allele associated with thinner frontal cortex in middle age. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, *26*(Suppl 3), 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-2011-0002>
- Filbey, F. M., Slack, K. J., Sunderland, T. P., & Cohen, R. M. (2006). Functional magnetic resonance imaging and magnetoencephalography differences associated with APOE ϵ 4 in young healthy adults. *NeuroReport*, *17*(15), 1585. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.wnr.0000234745.27571.d1>

- Filippini, N., MacIntosh, B. J., Hough, M. G., Goodwin, G. M., Frisoni, G. B., Smith, S. M., Matthews, P. M., Beckmann, C. F., & Mackay, C. E. (2009). Distinct patterns of brain activity in young carriers of the *APOE*- ϵ 4 allele. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *106*(17), 7209–7214. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0811879106>
- Fischer, L., Molloy, E. N., Binette, A. P., Vockert, N., Marquardt, J., Pilar, A. P., Kreissl, M. C., Remz, J., Tremblay-Mercier, J., Poirier, J., Rajah, M. N., Villeneuve, S., Group, P.-A. R., & Maass, A. (2025). Precuneus activity during retrieval is positively associated with amyloid burden in cognitively normal older *APOE4* carriers. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *45*(6), e1408242024. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1408-24.2024>
- Fortel, I., Butler, M., Korthauer, L. E., Zhan, L., Ajilore, O., Sidiropoulos, A., Wu, Y., Driscoll, I., Schonfeld, D., & Leow, A. (2022). Inferring excitation-inhibition dynamics using a maximum entropy model unifying brain structure and function. *Network Neuroscience*, *6*(2), 420–444. https://doi.org/10.1162/netn_a_00220
- Fortel, I., Korthauer, L. E., Morrissey, Z., Zhan, L., Ajilore, O., Wolfson, O., Driscoll, I., Schonfeld, D., & Leow, A. (2020). Connectome signatures of hyperexcitation in cognitively intact middle-aged female *APOE*- ϵ 4 carriers. *Cerebral Cortex*, *30*(12), 6350–6362. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhaa190>
- Foster, J. K., Albrecht, M. A., Savage, G., Lautenschlager, N. T., Ellis, K. A., Maruff, P., Szoek, C., Taddei, K., Martins, R., Masters, C. L., Ames, D., & AIBL Research Group. (2013). Lack of reliable evidence for a distinctive ϵ 4-related cognitive phenotype that is independent from clinical diagnostic status: Findings from the Australian Imaging, Biomarkers and Lifestyle Study. *Brain*, *136*(7), 2201–2216. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awt127>

- Fouquet, M., Besson, F. L., Gonneaud, J., La Joie, R., & Chételat, G. (2014). Imaging brain effects of APOE4 in cognitively normal individuals across the lifespan. *Neuropsychology Review*, 24(3), 290–299. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11065-014-9263-8>
- Gamache, J., Yun, Y., & Chiba-Falek, O. (2020). Sex-dependent effect of APOE on Alzheimer's disease and other age-related neurodegenerative disorders. *Disease Models & Mechanisms*, 13(8), dmm045211. <https://doi.org/10.1242/dmm.045211>
- Genin, E., Hannequin, D., Wallon, D., Sleegers, K., Hiltunen, M., Combarros, O., Bullido, M. J., Engelborghs, S., De Deyn, P., Berr, C., Pasquier, F., Dubois, B., Tognoni, G., Fiévet, N., Brouwers, N., Bettens, K., Arosio, B., Coto, E., Del Zompo, M., ... Campion, D. (2011). APOE and Alzheimer disease: A major gene with semi-dominant inheritance. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 16(9), 903–907. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2011.52>
- Goveas, J. S., Xie, C., Chen, G., Li, W., Ward, B. D., Franczak, M. B., Jones, J. L., Antuono, P. G., & Li, S.-J. (2013). Functional network endophenotypes unravel the effects of apolipoprotein E epsilon 4 in middle-aged adults. *PLOS ONE*, 8(2), e55902. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0055902>
- Guidotti Breting, L., Tuminello, E., & Han, S. D. (2011). Functional neuroimaging studies in normal aging. *Current Topics in Behavioral Neurosciences*, 10, 91–111. https://doi.org/10.1007/7854_2011_139
- Habib, M., Mak, E., Gabel, S., Su, L., Williams, G., Waldman, A., Wells, K., Ritchie, K., Ritchie, C., & O'Brien, J. T. (2017). Functional neuroimaging findings in healthy middle-aged adults at risk of Alzheimer's disease. *Ageing Research Reviews*, 36, 88–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2017.03.004>
- Han, S. D., & Bondi, M. W. (2008). Revision of the apolipoprotein E compensatory mechanism recruitment hypothesis. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 4(4), 251–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2008.02.006>

- Heise, V., Filippini, N., Ebmeier, K. P., & MacKay, C. E. (2011). The *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ allele modulates brain white matter integrity in healthy adults. *Molecular Psychiatry*, *16*(9), 908–916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2010.90>
- Heise, V., Offer, A., Whiteley, W., Mackay, C. E., Armitage, J. M., & Parish, S. (2024). A comprehensive analysis of *APOE* genotype effects on human brain structure in the UK Biobank. *Translational Psychiatry*, *14*(1), 143. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02848-5>
- Hodgetts, C. J., Shine, J. P., Williams, H., Postans, M., Sims, R., Williams, J., Lawrence, A. D., & Graham, K. S. (2019). Increased posterior default mode network activity and structural connectivity in young adult *APOE*- $\epsilon 4$ carriers: A multimodal imaging investigation. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *73*, 82–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2018.08.026>
- Honea, R. A., Vidoni, E., Harsha, A., & Burns, J. M. (2009). Impact of APOE on the healthy aging brain: A voxel-based MRI and DTI study. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease: JAD*, *18*(3), 553–564. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-2009-1163>
- Huang, Y., & Mahley, R. W. (2014). Apolipoprotein E: Structure and function in lipid metabolism, neurobiology, and Alzheimer's diseases. *Neurobiology of Disease*, *72*, 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbd.2014.08.025>
- Insausti, R., & Amaral, D. G. (2012). Chapter 24—Hippocampal formation. In J. K. Mai & G. Paxinos (Eds.), *The human nervous system* (3rd Ed., pp. 896–942). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-374236-0.10024-0>
- Jagust, W. J., & Mormino, E. C. (2011). Lifespan brain activity, β -amyloid, and Alzheimer's disease. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(11), 520–526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.09.004>

- Jansen, W. J., Janssen, O., Tijms, B. M., Vos, S. J. B., Ossenkoppele, R., Visser, P. J., & Amyloid Biomarker Study Group. (2022). Prevalence estimates of amyloid abnormality across the Alzheimer disease clinical spectrum. *JAMA Neurology*, *79*(3), 228–243. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2021.5216>
- Jansen, W. J., Ossenkoppele, R., Knol, D. L., Tijms, B. M., Scheltens, P., Verhey, F. R. J., Visser, P. J., Aalten, P., Aarsland, D., Alcolea, D., Alexander, M., Almdahl, I. S., Arnold, S. E., Baldeiras, I., Barthel, H., Berckel, B. N. M. van, Bibeau, K., Blennow, K., Brooks, D. J., ... Zetterberg, H. (2015). Prevalence of cerebral amyloid pathology in persons without dementia: A meta-analysis. *JAMA*, *313*(19), 1924–1938. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.4668>
- Johnson, S. C., Ries, M. L., Hess, T. M., Carlsson, C. M., Gleason, C. E., Alexander, A. L., Rowley, H. A., Asthana, S., & Sager, M. A. (2007). Effect of Alzheimer disease risk on brain function during self-appraisal in healthy middle-aged adults. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, *64*(10), 1163–1171. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.64.10.1163>
- Johnson, S. C., Schmitz, T. W., Trivedi, M. A., Ries, M. L., Torgerson, B. M., Carlsson, C. M., Asthana, S., Hermann, B. P., & Sager, M. A. (2006). The influence of Alzheimer disease family history and apolipoprotein E ϵ 4 on mesial temporal lobe activation. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *26*(22), 6069–6076. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0959-06.2006>
- Korthauer, L. E., Zhan, L., Ajilore, O., Leow, A., & Driscoll, I. (2018). Disrupted topology of the resting state structural connectome in middle-aged APOE ϵ 4 carriers. *NeuroImage*, *178*, 295–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.05.052>
- Kucikova, L., Xiong, X., Reinecke, P., Madden, J., Jackson, E., Tappin, O., Huang, W., Dounavi, M.-E., & Su, L. (2024). The effects of *APOE ϵ 4* allele on cerebral structure, function, and related interactions with cognition in young adults. *Ageing Research Reviews*, *101*, 102510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2024.102510>

- Kunz, L., Schröder, T. N., Lee, H., Montag, C., Lachmann, B., Sariyska, R., Reuter, M., Stirnberg, R., Stöcker, T., Messing-Floeter, P. C., Fell, J., Doeller, C. F., & Axmacher, N. (2015). Reduced grid-cell-like representations in adults at genetic risk for Alzheimer's disease. *Science*, *350*(6259), 430–433. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac8128>
- Lacey, C., Paterson, T., Gawryluk, J. R., & Initiative, for the A. D. N. (2024). Impact of APOE- ϵ alleles on brain structure and cognitive function in healthy older adults: A VBM and DTI replication study. *PLOS ONE*, *19*(4), e0292576. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0292576>
- Lachman, M. E., Teshale, S., & Agrigoroaei, S. (2015). Midlife as a pivotal period in the life course: Balancing growth and decline at the crossroads of youth and old age. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, *39*(1), 20–31. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025414533223>
- Lancaster, C., Tabet, N., & Rusted, J. (2017). The elusive nature of APOE ϵ 4 in mid-adulthood: Understanding the cognitive profile. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, *23*(3), 239–253. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617716000990>
- LaPlume, A. A., Lissaman, R., Kearley, J., & Rajah, M. N. (2025). Brain health and episodic memory function at midlife: Exploring the effects of sex differences and menopause status. In J. H. Grafman (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of the Human Brain* (2nd ed., pp. 95–112). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-820480-1.00179-0>
- Li, W., Antuono, P. G., Xie, C., Chen, G., Jones, J. L., Ward, B. D., Singh, S. P., Franczak, M. B., Goveas, J. S., & Li, S.-J. (2014). Aberrant functional connectivity in Papez circuit correlates with memory performance in cognitively intact middle-aged APOE4 carriers. *Cortex*, *57*, 167–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2014.04.006>

- Liu, X., Dounavi, M.-E., Ritchie, K., Wells, K., Ritchie, C. W., Su, L., Muniz-Terrera, G., & O'Brien, J. T. (2021). Higher midlife CAIDE score is associated with increased brain atrophy in a cohort of cognitively healthy middle-aged individuals. *Journal of Neurology*, *268*(5), 1962–1971. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00415-020-10383-8>
- Lyall, D. M., Cox, S. R., Lyall, L. M., Celis-Morales, C., Cullen, B., Mackay, D. F., Ward, J., Strawbridge, R. J., McIntosh, A. M., Sattar, N., Smith, D. J., Cavanagh, J., Deary, I. J., & Pell, J. P. (2019). Association between *APOE* e4 and white matter hyperintensity volume, but not total brain volume or white matter integrity. *Brain Imaging and Behavior*, *14*, 1468–1476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11682-019-00069-9>
- Lyall, D. M., Harris, S. E., Bastin, M. E., Muñoz Maniega, S., Murray, C., Lutz, M. W., Saunders, A. M., Roses, A. D., Valdés Hernández, M. del C., Royle, N. A., Starr, J. M., Porteous, David. J., Wardlaw, J. M., & Deary, I. J. (2014). Alzheimer's disease susceptibility genes *APOE* and *TOMM40*, and brain white matter integrity in the Lothian Birth Cohort 1936. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *35*(6), 1513.e25-1513.e33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2014.01.006>
- Mahley, R. W. (1988). Apolipoprotein E: Cholesterol transport protein with expanding role in cell biology. *Science*, *240*(4852), 622–630. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.3283935>
- Mahley, R. W. (2016). Apolipoprotein E: From cardiovascular disease to neurodegenerative disorders. *Journal of Molecular Medicine*, *94*(7), 739–746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00109-016-1427-y>
- McDonough, I. M., Festini, S. B., & Wood, M. M. (2020). Risk for Alzheimer's disease: A review of long-term episodic memory encoding and retrieval fMRI studies. *Ageing Research Reviews*, *62*, 101133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arr.2020.101133>
- McKeever, A., Paris, A. F., Cullen, J., Hayes, L., Ritchie, C. W., Ritchie, K., Waldman, A. D., Wells, K., Busza, A., Carriere, I., O'Brien, J. T., & Su, L. (2020). Hippocampal subfield

- volumes in middle-aged adults at risk of dementia. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 75(4), 1211–1218. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-200238>
- Mitchell, K. J. (2017). Neurogenomics – Towards a more rigorous science. *European Journal of Neuroscience*, 47(2), 109–114. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/ejn.13801>
- Nemes, S., Logan, P. E., Manchella, M. K., Mundada, N. S., La Joie, R., Polsinelli, A. J., Hammers, D. B., Koeppe, R. A., Foroud, T. M., Nudelman, K. N., Eloyan, A., Iaccarino, L., Dorsant-Ardón, V., Taurone, A., Thangarajah, M., Dage, J. L., Aisen, P., Grinberg, L. T., Jack Jr., C. R., ... Leads, C. (2023). Sex and *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carrier effects on atrophy, amyloid PET, and tau PET burden in early-onset Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 19(S9), S49–S63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13403>
- Nerattini, M., Rubino, F., Jett, S., Andy, C., Boneu, C., Zarate, C., Carlton, C., Loeb-Zeitlin, S., Havryliuk, Y., Pahlajani, S., Williams, S., Berti, V., Christos, P., Fink, M., Dyke, J. P., Brinton, R. D., & Mosconi, L. (2023). Elevated gonadotropin levels are associated with increased biomarker risk of Alzheimer's disease in midlife women. *Frontiers in Dementia*, 2, 1303256. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frdem.2023.1303256>
- Neu, S. C., Pa, J., Kukull, W., Beekly, D., Kuzma, A., Gangadharan, P., Wang, L. S., Romero, K., Arneric, S. P., Redolfi, A., Orlandi, D., Frisoni, G. B., Au, R., Devine, S., Auerbach, S., Espinosa, A., Boada, M., Ruiz, A., Johnson, S. C., ... Toga, A. W. (2017). Apolipoprotein E genotype and sex risk factors for Alzheimer disease: A meta-analysis. *JAMA Neurology*, 74(10), 1178–1189. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2017.2188>
- Newton, C., Pope, M., Rua, C., Henson, R., Ji, Z., Burgess, N., Rodgers, C. T., Stangl, M., Dounavi, M.-E., Castegnaro, A., Koychev, I., Malhotra, P., Wolbers, T., Ritchie, K., Ritchie, C. W., O'Brien, J., Su, L., Chan, D., & for the PREVENT Dementia Research Programme. (2024). Entorhinal-based path integration selectively predicts midlife risk of

Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 20(4), 2779–2793.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13733>

O'Brien, J. T., Firbank, M. J., Ritchie, K., Wells, K., Williams, G. B., Ritchie, C. W., & Su, L. (2020). Association between midlife dementia risk factors and longitudinal brain atrophy: The PREVENT-Dementia study. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry*, 91(2), 158–161. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp-2019-321652>

O'Donoghue, M. C., Murphy, S. E., Zamboni, G., Nobre, A. C., & Mackay, C. E. (2018). APOE genotype and cognition in healthy individuals at-risk of Alzheimer's disease: A review. *Cortex*, 104, 103–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2018.03.025>

Okonkwo, O. C., Oh, J. M., Kosciak, R., Jonaitis, E., Cleary, C. A., Dowling, N. M., Bendlin, B. B., LaRue, A., Hermann, B. P., Barnhart, T. E., Murali, D., Rowley, H. A., Carlsson, C. M., Gallagher, C. L., Asthana, S., Sager, M. A., Christian, B. T., & Johnson, S. C. (2014). Amyloid burden, neuronal function, and cognitive decline in middle-aged adults at risk for Alzheimer's disease. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 20(4), 422–433. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617714000113>

Okonkwo, O. C., Xu, G., Dowling, N. M., Bendlin, B. B., LaRue, A., Hermann, B. P., Kosciak, R., Jonaitis, E., Rowley, H. A., Carlsson, C. M., Asthana, S., Sager, M. A., & Johnson, S. C. (2012). Family history of Alzheimer disease predicts hippocampal atrophy in healthy middle-aged adults. *Neurology*, 78(22), 1769. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0b013e3182583047>

Palmer, J. M., Huentelman, M., & Ryan, L. (2023). More than just risk for Alzheimer's disease: APOE ε4's impact on the aging brain. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 46(9), 750–763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tins.2023.06.003>

Panizzon, M. S., Hauger, R., Dale, A. M., Eaves, L. J., Eyler, L. T., Fischl, B., Fennema-Notestine, C., Franz, C. E., Grant, M. D., Jak, A. J., Jacobson, K. C., Lyons, M. J.,

- Mendoza, S. P., Neale, M. C., Prom-Wormley, E. C., Seidman, L. J., Tsuang, M. T., Xian, H., & Kremen, W. S. (2010). Testosterone modifies the effect of *APOE* genotype on hippocampal volume in middle-aged men. *Neurology*, *75*(10), 874. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0b013e3181f11deb>
- Park, D. C., & Festini, S. B. (2016). The middle-aged brain: A cognitive neuroscience perspective. In R. Cabeza, L. Nyberg, & D. C. Park (Eds.), *Cognitive neuroscience of aging: Linking cognitive and cerebral aging* (2nd Ed, pp. 363–388). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199372935.003.0015>
- Rajah, M. N., Wallace, L. M. K., Ankudowich, E., Yu, E. H., Swierkot, A., Patel, R., Chakravarty, M. M., Naumova, D., Pruessner, J., Joobar, R., Gauthier, S., & Pasvanis, S. (2017). Family history and APOE4 risk for Alzheimer’s disease impact the neural correlates of episodic memory by early midlife. *NeuroImage: Clinical*, *14*, 760–774. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2017.03.016>
- Rall, S. C., Weisgraber, K. H., & Mahley, R. W. (1982). Human apolipoprotein E. The complete amino acid sequence. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *257*(8), 4171–4178. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(18\)34702-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(18)34702-1)
- Reiman, E. M., Uecker, A., Caselli, R. J., Lewis, S., Bandy, D., De Leon, M. J., De Santi, S., Convit, A., Osborne, D., Weaver, A., & Thibodeau, S. N. (1998). Hippocampal volumes in cognitively normal persons at genetic risk for Alzheimer’s disease. *Annals of Neurology*, *44*(2), 288–291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.410440226>
- Ritchie, C. W., Bridgeman, K., Gregory, S., O’Brien, J. T., Danso, S. O., Dounavi, M.-E., Carriere, I., Driscoll, D., Hillary, R., Koychev, I., Lawlor, B., Naci, L., Su, L., Low, A., Mak, E., Malhotra, P., Manson, J., Marioni, R., Murphy, L., ... Ritchie, K. (2024). The PREVENT dementia programme: Baseline demographic, lifestyle, imaging and

- cognitive data from a midlife cohort study investigating risk factors for dementia. *Brain Communications*, 6(3), fcae189. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcae189>
- Ritchie, K., Carrière, I., Su, L., O'Brien, J. T., Lovestone, S., Wells, K., & Ritchie, C. W. (2017). The midlife cognitive profiles of adults at high risk of late-onset Alzheimer's disease: The PREVENT study. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 13(10), 1089–1097. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2017.02.008>
- Salvato, G. (2015). Does apolipoprotein E genotype influence cognition in middle-aged individuals? *Current Opinion in Neurology*, 28(6), 612–617. <https://doi.org/10.1097/WCO.0000000000000262>
- Shah, S. N., Dounavi, M.-E., Malhotra, P. A., Lawlor, B., Naci, L., Koychev, I., Ritchie, C. W., Ritchie, K., & O'Brien, J. T. (2024). Dementia risk and thalamic nuclei volumetry in healthy midlife adults: The PREVENT Dementia study. *Brain Communications*, 6(2), fcae046. <https://doi.org/10.1093/braincomms/fcae046>
- Shine, J. P., Hodgetts, C. J., Postans, M., Lawrence, A. D., & Graham, K. S. (2015). APOE-ε4 selectively modulates posteromedial cortex activity during scene perception and short-term memory in young healthy adults. *Scientific Reports*, 5, 16322. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16322>
- Smith, G. E., Bohac, D. L., Waring, S. C., Kokmen, E., Tangalos, E. G., Ivnik, R. J., & Petersen, R. C. (1998). Apolipoprotein E genotype influences cognitive “phenotype” in patients with Alzheimer's disease but not in healthy control subjects. *Neurology*, 50(2), 355–362. <https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.50.2.355>
- Sperling, R. A., Donohue, M. C., Raman, R., Sun, C.-K., Yaari, R., Holdridge, K., Siemers, E., Johnson, K. A., Aisen, P. S., & for the A4 Study Team. (2020). Association of factors with elevated amyloid burden in clinically normal older individuals. *JAMA Neurology*, 77(6), 735–745. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaneurol.2020.0387>

- Suri, S., Mackay, C. E., Kelly, M. E., Germuska, M., Tunbridge, E. M., Frisoni, G. B., Matthews, P. M., Ebmeier, K. P., Bulte, D. P., & Filippini, N. (2015). Reduced cerebrovascular reactivity in young adults carrying the *APOE* ϵ 4 allele. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, *11*(6), 648-657.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2014.05.1755>
- Thurston, R. C., Thomas, H. N., Castle, A. J., & Gibson, C. J. (2025). Menopause as a biological and psychological transition. *Nature Reviews Psychology*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44159-025-00463-9>
- Trachtenberg, A. J., Filippini, N., Cheeseman, J., Duff, E. P., Neville, M. J., Ebmeier, K. P., Karpe, F., & Mackay, C. E. (2012). The effects of APOE on brain activity do not simply reflect the risk of Alzheimer's disease. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *33*(3), 618.e1-618.e13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2010.11.011>
- Trachtenberg, A. J., Filippini, N., Ebmeier, K. P., Smith, S. M., Karpe, F., & Mackay, C. E. (2012). The effects of *APOE* on the functional architecture of the resting brain. *NeuroImage*, *59*(1), 565–572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2011.07.059>
- Trachtenberg, A. J., Filippini, N., & Mackay, C. E. (2012). The effects of APOE- ϵ 4 on the BOLD response. *Neurobiology of Aging*, *33*(2), 323–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2010.03.009>
- Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., Moher, D., Peters, M. D. J., Horsley, T., Weeks, L., Hempel, S., Akl, E. A., Chang, C., McGowan, J., Stewart, L., Hartling, L., Aldcroft, A., Wilson, M. G., Garritty, C., ... Straus, S. E. (2018). PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and explanation. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, *169*(7), 467–473. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>
- Trivedi, M. A., Schmitz, T. W., Ries, M. L., Torgerson, B. M., Sager, M. A., Hermann, B. P., Asthana, S., & Johnson, S. C. (2006). Reduced hippocampal activation during episodic

- encoding in middle-aged individuals at genetic risk of Alzheimer's Disease: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Medicine*, 4, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-4-1>
- Tuminello, E. R., & Han, S. D. (2011). The apolipoprotein e antagonistic pleiotropy hypothesis: Review and recommendations. *International Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 2011, 726197. <https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/726197>
- Valencia-Olvera, A. C., Maldonado Weng, J., Christensen, A., LaDu, M. J., & Pike, C. J. (2023). Role of estrogen in women's Alzheimer's disease risk as modified by *APOE*. *Journal of Neuroendocrinology*, 35(2), e13209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jne.13209>
- Weisgraber, K. H., Rall, S. C., & Mahley, R. W. (1981). Human E apoprotein heterogeneity. Cysteine-arginine interchanges in the amino acid sequence of the apo-E isoforms. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 256(17), 9077–9083. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(19\)52510-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(19)52510-8)
- Xu, G., McLaren, D. G., Ries, M. L., Fitzgerald, M. E., Bendlin, B. B., Rowley, H. A., Sager, M. A., Atwood, C., Asthana, S., & Johnson, S. C. (2009). The influence of parental history of Alzheimer's disease and apolipoprotein E 4 on the BOLD signal during recognition memory. *Brain*, 132(2), 383–391. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awn254>
- Young, P. N. E., Estarellas, M., Coomans, E., Srikrishna, M., Beaumont, H., Maass, A., Venkataraman, A. V., Lissaman, R., Jiménez, D., Betts, M. J., McGlinchey, E., Berron, D., O'Connor, A., Fox, N. C., Pereira, J. B., Jagust, W., Carter, S. F., Paterson, R. W., & Schöll, M. (2020). Imaging biomarkers in neurodegeneration: Current and future practices. *Alzheimer's Research & Therapy*, 12(1), 49. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13195-020-00612-7>
- Zokaei, N., Giehl, K., Sillence, A., Neville, M. J., Karpe, F., Nobre, A. C., & Husain, M. (2017). Sex and APOE: A memory advantage in male APOE ϵ 4 carriers in midlife. *Cortex*, 88, 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2016.12.016>

Dowell et al. (2016)	37 (17 ϵ 4+)	43-58	Cross-sectional	ROI (parahippocampus, cuneus, anterior cingulate, precuneus, posterior cingulate, hippocampus)	(1) No difference in ROI (WM) volumes (2) Thicker parahippocampal cortex in ϵ 4+
Evans et al. (2020)	32 (16 ϵ 4+)	45-55	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in hippocampal volume
Fennema-Notestine et al. (2011)	482 (125 ϵ 4+)	51-59	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain & ROI (assorted medial temporal, lateral temporal, and frontal regions)	(1) Thinner frontal cortices in ϵ 4+ (2) Thicker fusiform cortex in ϵ 4+
Goveas et al. (2013)	46 (20 ϵ 4+)	44-65	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analysis

Johnson et al. (2006)	132 (48 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analysis
Johnson et al. (2007)	110 (39 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analysis
Li et al. (2014)	46 (20 ϵ 4+)	44-65	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analysis (2) No difference in hippocampal volume
Liu et al. (2021)	160 (61 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Longitudinal	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in total GM or WM volume at baseline or two-year follow-up (2) No difference in total cortical thickness
McKeever et al. (2020)	150 (57 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampal subfields)	(1) No difference in hippocampal subfield volumes
Nemes et al. (2023)	77 (33+ ϵ 4+)	40-64	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analyses (males or females, respectively) (2) No difference in hippocampal volume

Nerattini et al. (2023)	191 (86+ ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	ROI (frontal regions)	(1) No difference in frontal GM volume
Newton et al. (2024)	53 (18 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Cross-sectional	ROI (entorhinal cortex + subregions, hippocampal subfields, retrosplenial cortex, posterior cingulate)	(1) No difference in ROI volumes
O'Brien et al. (2020)	165 (64 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Longitudinal	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in brain volume change
Okonkwo et al. (2012)	108 (35 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Longitudinal	Whole-brain & ROI (posterior cingulate, hippocampus, parahippocampal gyrus, amygdala)	(1) No difference in ROI-restricted VBM analysis at baseline or four-year follow-up (2) Lower right middle temporal gyrus GM density in ϵ 4+ (exploratory whole-brain VBM analysis)
Okonkwo et al. (2014)	122 (48+ ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in hippocampal volume

Panizzon et al. (2010)	375 (94+ ϵ 4+)	51-59	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) Lower hippocampal volume in ϵ 4+ (only when <i>APOE</i> -testosterone interaction present)
Rajah et al. (2017)	49 (11 ϵ 4+)	41-58	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in hippocampal volume
Reiman et al. (1998)	33 (11 ϵ 4+)	50-62	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in hippocampal volume (2) No difference in left-right asymmetry of hippocampal volume
Ritchie et al. (2017)	208 (75+ ϵ 4+)	40-59	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in total brain volume of whole-brain grey matter (2) No difference in hippocampal volume
Shah et al. (2024)	611 (235 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Cross-sectional	ROI (thalamus + subregions)	(1) No difference in thalamus volume (2) No difference in thalamic subregion volumes
Trivedi et al. (2006)	40 (23 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	ROI (medial temporal lobe)	(1) No difference in ROI-restricted VBM analysis

Xu et al. (2009)	74 (33 $\epsilon 4+$)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in whole-brain VBM analysis
------------------	------------------------	-------	-----------------	-------------	---

Note. Sample *N* reflects the total number of cognitively healthy middle-aged participants reportedly included in relevant *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analyses. The number of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers ($\epsilon 4+$) is provided in parentheses. Age range is reported in years and reflects the stated age range of the included participants or, if unavailable, the age range used for (initial) recruitment. We did not differentiate between studies adopting different definitions of *APOE* $\epsilon 4+$ (e.g., $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ vs. $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4 + \epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$). For studies with multiple groups (e.g., FH+/ $\epsilon 4+$, FH-/ $\epsilon 4+$, etc.), we summed across carrier/non-carrier groups. For studies reporting the percentage of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers, we used the reported sample sizes to calculate values and, where necessary, rounded to the nearest whole number (indicated by ⁺). Design reflects the cross-sectional or longitudinal nature of the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analysis and not necessarily the overall design of the study.

Abbreviations: *APOE* = apolipoprotein-E; FH = family history of dementia; GM = grey matter; ROI = region of interest; VBM = voxel-based morphometry; WM = white matter.

Table 2. Summary of studies examining *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in brain function at midlife.

Study	Sample <i>N</i>	Age range	Design	Task(s)	Analytical approach	Key <i>APOE</i> $\epsilon 4$ result(s)
Evans et al. (2013)	36 (17 $\epsilon 4+$)	43-58	Cross-sectional	Covert attention	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus, extrastriate visual areas, inferior parietal areas, anterior cingulate areas, right middle frontal areas)	(1) Lower activation in extrastriate cortex independent of cue type (valid, invalid) among $\epsilon 4+$
Evans et al. (2014)	40 (19 $\epsilon 4+$)	43-58	Cross-sectional	Prospective memory, covert attention	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus, superior parietal areas)	(1) Lower activation in extrastriate cortex and right superior parietal lobule during prospective memory trials among $\epsilon 4+$ (2) No difference in activation for validity effect (valid trial mean RTs)

						- invalid trial mean RTs) on covert attention task
Evans et al. (2020)	32 (16 ϵ 4+)	45-55	Cross-sectional	Old/new recognition	Whole-brain & ROI (hippocampus, parahippocampus)	(1) No difference in activation for subsequent memory effects (2) Greater activation in left hippocampus (subiculum) for remembered vs. forgotten items in ϵ 4- but not ϵ 4+
Johnson et al. (2006)	132 (48 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Old/new recognition	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in activation for novelty effect (new > old)
Johnson et al. (2007)	110 (39 ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Self-appraisal	Whole-brain	(1) Greater activation for referential self-appraisal in left superior frontal gyrus, left anterior cingulate, and retrosplenial areas among ϵ 4+ with negative FH

						(2) No difference in activation for referential self-appraisal (restricted to regions not showing interaction)
Newton et al. (2024)	53 (18 ϵ 4+)	40-59	Cross-sectional	Spatial memory	ROI (posteromedial entorhinal cortex)	(1) No difference in grid cell-like activation
Okonkwo et al. (2014)	122 (48+ ϵ 4+)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Old/new recognition	ROI (precuneus, posterior cingulate)	(1) No difference in activation for familiarity effect (old > new)
Rajah et al. (2017)	51 (11 ϵ 4+)	41-58	Cross-sectional	Spatial context memory	Whole-brain	(1) Greater activation in right hippocampus during low-load encoding among ϵ 4+ with positive FH (2) Greater encoding-related activation and lower retrieval related activation in fusiform cortex among ϵ 4+ with positive FH

Trivedi et al. (2006)	40 (23 $\epsilon 4+$)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Old/new recognition	Whole-brain & ROI (medial temporal lobe)	(1) Lower activation for novelty effect (new > old) in right hippocampus among $\epsilon 4+$ (2) No difference in activation for familiarity effect (old > new)
Xu et al. (2009)	74 (33 $\epsilon 4+$)	40-65	Cross-sectional	Old/new recognition	Whole-brain	(1) Lower activation for familiarity effect (old > new) in left dorsal posterior cingulate/precuneus among $\epsilon 4+$ (2) Lower activation for faces (old or new) in left anterior cingulate gyrus among $\epsilon 4+$

Note. Sample *N* reflects the total number of cognitively healthy middle-aged participants reportedly included in relevant *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analyses. The number of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers ($\epsilon 4+$) is provided in parentheses. Age range is reported in years and reflects the stated age range of the included participants or, if unavailable, the age range used for (initial) recruitment. We did not differentiate between studies adopting different definitions of *APOE* $\epsilon 4+$ (e.g., $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ vs. $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4 + \epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$). For studies with multiple groups (e.g., FH+/ $\epsilon 4+$, FH-/ $\epsilon 4+$, etc.), we summed across carrier/non-carrier groups. For studies reporting the percentage of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers, we used the reported sample sizes to calculate values and, where necessary, rounded to the nearest whole number (indicated by ⁺). Design reflects the cross-sectional or longitudinal nature of the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analysis and not necessarily the overall design of the study. For Task, we used our own labels and not necessarily those provided by the authors.

This helps to highlight commonalities across studies, where they exist. Abbreviations: *APOE* = apolipoprotein-E; FH = family history of dementia; ROI = region of interest; RTs = reaction times.

Table 3. Summary of studies examining *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related differences in brain structural/functional connectivity at midlife.

Study	Sample <i>N</i>	Age range	Design	Analytical approach	Key <i>APOE</i> $\epsilon 4$ result(s)
Dowell et al. (2016)	37 (17 $\epsilon 4+$)	43-58	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) No difference in 8 resting-state networks
Evans et al. (2020)	32 (16 $\epsilon 4+$)	45-55	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) No difference in hippocampal ODI
Fortel et al. (2022)	76 (38 $\epsilon 4+$)	40-60	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) Global shift toward hyper-excitation in rs-SC among female (but not male) $\epsilon 4+$ (2) Lower tolerance to network dysfunction among female (but not male) $\epsilon 4+$
Fortel et al. (2020)	76 (38 $\epsilon 4+$)	40-60	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) Global shift toward hyper-excitation in rs-SC among $\epsilon 4+$ (2) Shift toward hyper-excitation across several ROIs comprising the rs-SC among female (but not male) $\epsilon 4+$, starting at age 50

Goveas et al. (2013)	46 (20 ϵ 4+)	44-65	Cross-sectional	ROI (DMN: posterior cingulate, ECN: dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, SN: orbital anterior insula)	(1) Lower DMN connectivity among ϵ 4+ (2) Lower ECN connectivity among ϵ 4+ (3) Greater SN connectivity among ϵ 4+
Korthauer et al. (2018)	76 (38 ϵ 4+)	40-60	Cross-sectional	Whole-brain	(1) Lower global and local efficiency in rs-SC among ϵ 4+ (2) Greater betweenness centrality of right putamen and right thalamus, as well as greater participation coefficient of the right thalamus, in rs-SC among ϵ 4+ (3) Lower betweenness centrality of left lateral orbitofrontal cortex and left superior temporal gyrus, as well as lower participation coefficient of the left lateral

					orbitofrontal cortex and left superior frontal cortex, in rs-SC among $\epsilon 4+$
					(4) In targeted failure analysis, greater resilience evident in $\epsilon 4+$ until 10% of hubs removed, then lower resilience as central nodes removed
Li et al. (2014)	46 (20 $\epsilon 4+$)	44-65	Cross-sectional	ROI (hippocampus)	(1) Lower functional connectivity between hippocampus and various regions (caudate, thalamus, posterior cingulate, superior frontal gyrus, lentiform nucleus, medial frontal gyrus, insula, anterior cingulate corte, culmen of cerebellum) among $\epsilon 4+$

Note. Sample N reflects the total number of cognitively healthy middle-aged participants reportedly included in relevant *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analyses. The number of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers ($\epsilon 4+$) is provided in parentheses. Age range is reported in years and reflects the stated age range of the included participants or, if unavailable, the age range used for (initial) recruitment. We did not differentiate between studies adopting different definitions of *APOE* $\epsilon 4+$ (e.g., $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ vs. $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4 + \epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$). For studies with multiple groups (e.g., FH+/ $\epsilon 4+$, FH-/ $\epsilon 4+$, etc.), we summed across carrier/non-carrier groups. For studies reporting the percentage of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers, we used the reported sample sizes to calculate values and, where necessary, rounded to the nearest whole number (indicated by $^+$). Design reflects the cross-sectional or longitudinal nature of the *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ analysis and not necessarily the overall design of the study.

Abbreviations: *APOE* = apolipoprotein-E; DMN = default mode network; ECN = executive control network; FH = family history of dementia; ODI = orientation dispersion index; ROI = region of interest; rs-SC = resting-state structural connectome; SN = salience network.

Figure Captions

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram for the scoping review.

Figure 2. Age range in midlife *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ studies. Studies are listed by first author name and year of publication, arranged alphabetically. Circles represent minimum and maximum age values, while lines represent the full range. The ranges shown here reflect the full age range of the included participants or, if not available, the age range used for recruitment.